

Superstring theory could be already correct

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Superstring theory might already be correct, but not in the way you probably imagined. There is a way that a form of superstring theory could already be the correct structure underpinning the Standard Model and gravity. To see how, one needs to appreciate the only truly critical aspect of supersymmetry is anomaly cancellation. In 4D spacetime curing the anomalies requires a ratio of 1::4::6 elementary bosons to fermions zero Fradkin–Tseytlin scalars. The CPT-symmetric LR-symmetric Standard Model augmented with 2×36 dimension zero Fradkin–Tseytlin scalars is such a model: the Weyl, trace and vacuum energy anomalies cancel, with the benefit of eliminating the graviton and the Higgs. Gravity must be a hydrodynamics of the fine structure of spacetime, and the Higgs a composite “particle.” There already exists a stringy theory with all these characteristics, and moreover in a minimalist way. This theory has the added benefit of shedding a new light on the meaning of quantum mechanics.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Spacetime minimalism satisfying 4D supersymmetry requires 4 fermions and 6 scalars for each boson [1]. These ratios are satisfied by a CPT-symmetric left-right symmetric Standard model, moreover by a model that contains all the other gauge symmetries that are empirically known to be fundamental, all in a Clifford algebra with a “doubled” Lorentz frame [2]. Assuming there are

A Clifford algebra in an abstract 8-dimensional complex frame-field space could be loosely thought of by a reasonable philosopher as a doubled 4D spacetime. The vierbein or tetrad gets doubled. Just thinking semi-numerologically for now, one may proceed to develop an algebraic Standard Model with the above characteristics using gauge fibre bundle theory as the framework, but there is another possibility that is *stringy*.

The speculation of this *purely philosophical* paper is that we can impose a spacetime geometric account for

¹ Moreover, for conformally coupled UV complete theories such FT scalars seem to be required for other reasons in the context of twistor theory [5].

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the complexified Cl_3 algebra. In doing so we have a manifestly supersymmetric string theory, but in Einstein’s 4-dimensional spacetime. The catch is that this spacetime is not everywhere locally Minkowski. This turns out to be an incredible feature rather than a bug, because it *explains all of quantum mechanics*. To deflate that last remark, and as will be evident in the following sections, we will attenuate our conclusions by noting that by “explains” here we mean philosophically and conceptually.

It should also be born in mind that no existing theory of fundamental physics is everywhere locally Minkowski, not if one regards the fields as “living on spacetime,” since there are no such fields in Minkowski spacetime. Alternatively, if one regards spacetime as a fiction and emergent from pure computational automata or field Idealism of some variety, then spacetime is “not even Minkowski.”

This work is not yet at a status one could reasonably regard as established theoretical physics. We are leaning upon shoulders of giants, and only should there be no fatal flaws in our logic will we be sitting upon their shoulders, and then only when experiments can confirm the RH neutrino is dark matter, and that gravity is already a quantum theory (without a graviton) then we might deign to stand up upon those shoulders.

In §-III we provide a brief overview of the algebra of the *nearly* minimal LR-symmetric Standard Model (SM). In §-II a stringy ontology is matched up with this algebra, this is known as Topological 4-Geon theory or T4G. In §-II.A we “explain” (meaning in conceptual terms) why gravity is already a quantum theory in the T4G framework. In §-IV some puzzles to do with gravity, the Higgs and the vacuum are discussed for interests of advancing upon the preceding ideas. There is ample room, we feel, for further speculation and experimental exploration directions launching off the ideas in this paper.

This paper is a high-level overview of several prior preprints on topological 4-geon theory (T4G) [2, 6, 7]. We thus take the liberty of skipping a few details for brevity. However, what was not previously reported upon, except in Blood’s work [8], is a theory of interactions and couplings. This will be our main new focus in §-V, though necessarily still philosophical.

II. TOPOLOGICAL 4-GEON THEORY

T4G [6] is a minimalist 4D spacetime theory of quantum mechanics. It includes GR as a classical limit (the “hydrodynamics” of the Standard Model, see [9, 10]) and which has quantum mechanics (QM) as a sub-model of the cobordism boundaries. This is described in the paper [6] and so needs no further elaboration on the basics, but we will mention a few things towards the purpose of the present paper.

T4G defines special classes of spacetime cobordisms, which are partial cobordisms, not the entirety of spacetime between two global Cauchy hypersurfaces, but

merely the restricted region of two light-cones relevant to some “measurement process.” Thus, in the T4G theory, QM is a theory of measurement processes.

To the extent a measurement process is incompletely defined or ill-defined², so is the corresponding quantum mechanics seen as an application to *that* measurement process.

One crucial note is that $QM \subset T4G$, precisely because in T4G theory we obtain QM by “throwing away” the interior of a T4G-cobordism region — defined as the region of spacetime involving a time-evolution account of some measurement process, with two time boundaries t_1 =set-up, t_2 =recording. The quickest way to see T4G is a quantum theory (according to standard Dirac–von Neumann axioms, or even easier, by the generalized probability theory (GPT) framework axioms [generalized probability theory] [11]) is to note T4G theory admits continuous reversible state transitions. By the GPT results this implies entanglement and superposition, and hence interference. This is however particle phenomenology agnostic, and hence a great advantage of T4G theory is that it most naturally adopts a doubled spacetime Clifford algebra, which yields precisely the known LR-symmetric Standard Model phenomenology [2, 8, 12] — at least up to fine details over the mechanism of electroweak symmetry breaking and the correct form of the triality automorphism.

It is (mostly) because the QM theory derived from T4G theory excludes data from the T4G-cobordism interior that QM is *considered* as a stochastic transition process theory, and is exactly equivalent (in this respect) to Barandes’ ISQM³ (up to some conjectured category functor of some sort, as yet not fully defined in the literature).

T4G has two aspects which may be studied somewhat separately,

1. In bare T4G-cobordism theory we only consider generic measurement processes, this is the ISQM aspect. It is particle phenomenology agnostic. The focus is on the logic of measurement processes.
2. More recently some particle phenomenology has been possible from a T4G point of view, thanks to the work on Clifford algebra, mainly by Gresnigt et al [14] [12] and Jason Blood [8].

The bare bones T4G studies, for example, can include the EPR effect [7], and thus potentially also most other effects which prove non-classical features of reality (Kochen–Specker, PBR, quantum Zeno effect, and other standard results from quantum information technology studies). Simple Clifford algebra frameworks (such as

² All practical experiments we perform are in fact not well-defined, owing to our data gathering and precision engineering limitations, quite apart from *further* quantum mechanical limitations.

³ *Indivisible Stochastic Quantum Mechanics*, see [13].

the STA (spacetime algebra) [15]) cannot accommodate these effects without additional non-local correlator axioms. In practice the latter just means writing down spin-coupled spinors, but we feel it should be noted that there is no spacetime meaning given to such coupling or bipartite structure in the raw algebra of the STA ($\mathcal{Cl}_{3,1}$ or \mathcal{Cl}_4). We are departing from the raw {STA + superposition} picture to seek a spacetime account — rather than a mere algebraic statement — for the entanglement.

In this paper we are interested in the interplay between *both* of these aspects of T4G theory.

II.A. Indivisible Stochastic QM

The relations between Barandes’ Indivisible Stochastic QM and T4G theory were discussed in [6], and need no embellishment here.

The key idea in this framework (ISQM) is that the ‘quantum state’ is not a fundamental element of reality, and so, for example, the Pusey–Barrett–Rudolph (PBR) theorem is moot, since there are no ‘quantum states’ *per se*. This is in full agreement with how T4G theory interprets the spinors. We interpret spinors as in David Hestenes’ view [16–18]:— they are transformation instructions, nothing more. In this T4G context the spinors are acting upon the algebra of observables, not the other way around, which is something most clearly seen in the correspondence between the Clifford algebra sandwich products (which are mirror reflections and rotations) and the Dirac bra-ket. This was also discussed in [6].

In ISQM the superpositions are also not real *per se*, but are instead stochastic effects of indivisibility. The phenomena the superpositions describe, and the phenomena the spinors as-transform-instructions describe are entirely physical, so T4G is not anti-realist, and T4G eschews the Copenhagen interpretation. Barandes does not provide any ontology for indivisibility (i.e., failure of the stochastic transition matrix to factorize at an intermediate time). But almost any reasonable theory of entanglement would accord with Barandes’ ISQM framework (since entanglement is just failure of the spacetime cobordism to be divisible, and every quantum theory has a spacetime cobordism, even if only as a convenient ‘emergent’ fiction). We have argued [6] that T4G provides a good ontology for indivisibility — in wormhole topology around the Planck scale. Although, T4G allows some weak reality to superpositions (which maybe could be manifested in sensitive Three-Slit interference patterns, though we would be agnostic about the results).

In concert with GPT frameworks, Barandes has that entanglement is in a sense more fundamental and “real,” or he could also say “spacetime indivisibility” is what is the real essence of QM. These are more or less the same thing in T4G. Similarly in GPT frameworks, entan-

glement and superposition are (more-or-less⁴) equivalent [19] phenomena.

III. THE 8-FOLD CLIFFORD WAY

For just the algebra, the bare minimum appears to require complexified spacetime, we discuss this in §-V.A of [2]. However, we claimed in the introduction that this model is only nearly minimal. This turns out to be a crucial feature rather than a bug (one of several instances of that aphorism in this paper).

In a previous paper [2] on spacetime algebra and topology of putative 4-geons, we matched T4G theory to a complexified Clifford algebra in 8-dimensions, denoted \mathcal{Cl}_8 . In any complexified Clifford algebra the metric signature is arbitrary, and so this model can always be interpreted as $\mathcal{Cl}_{4,4}$ or colloquially “doubled spacetime frames.” This is how we view the combination of T4G with Clifford algebra.

Loosely speaking (not yet formalized) the complex structure provides not only desirable analyticity for the spinor transforms, but also an algebraic conduit for communication across the wormholes connecting the two spacetime frames.

Our contention that T4G is a “stringy theory” derives from the above two sections, (1) T4G needs wormhole topology for the bare-bones *logic of quantum mechanics*, as discussed by Hadley back in 1997 [20, 21]. and (2) the minimal Clifford algebra fitting T4G doubled spacetime frames (two ends of the wormholes in putative 4-geon structures) provides the symmetries of the known Standard Model, if we may include a right-handed neutrino. What is stringy about T4G theory? The wormholes are stringy, since for the EPR effect we require information can propagate across the 4-geon wormholes [7] without violating the topological censorship conjectures [22, 23]. The Standard Model path integral is already accounting for these wormhole worldsheets.

III.A. The doubled Standard Model

The Witt basis we have explored is defined by two sets of STA fiducial frames, $\{e_\mu, f_\mu\}$, via Witt ladder operators q and q^\dagger . To spare typesetting a lot of daggers I have preferred to use capital Q for q^\dagger . In the geometric

⁴ The “less equivalent” is all in how valid GPT frameworks are for universal quantum mechanics, which is non-trivial because GPT frameworks presume existence of a classical measurement instrument. One cannot therefore *derive* some things, like classical correspondence, from GPTs.

algebra for $\mathbb{C}l_8 \cong \mathcal{C}l_{0,1} \otimes \mathcal{C}l_8$ we define,

$$\begin{aligned} q_0 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_4 - e_3), & Q_0 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_4 + e_3), \\ q_1 &= (-e_1 - ie_2), & Q_1 &= (e_1 - ie_2), \\ q_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_4 - f_3), & Q_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_4 + f_3), \\ q_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(-f_1 - if_2), & Q_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_1 - if_2). \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

One can check these satisfy the defining properties for a Witt basis,

$$\{q_i, q_j\} = 0, \quad \{q_i^\dagger, q_j^\dagger\} = 0, \quad \{q_i, q_j^\dagger\} = \delta_{ij}$$

we could also recover the orthonormal basis using the inverse to the above relations. The convention is to identify $\{e_\mu\} \equiv \{\gamma_\mu\}$ as the locally spacetime frame (and STA fiducial frame), and the reciprocal frame to the Dirac gamma matrices (in the $\mathcal{C}l_{3,1}$ category the functor from the Hilbert space maps Dirac matrices to the Clifford basis vectors and the pseudoscalar $I = e_0 e_1 e_2 e_3$).

Minimal semi-classical QM — according to T4G theory — consists of performing transformations by scaled rotors, $\psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{I\beta} R$, on the algebra of observables. (Here I is the STA pseudoscalar, so the factor $e^{I\beta}$ is like a rotor, but technically more like a duality transformation, mixing particle and anti-particle, at least in the reduced Dirac theory in $\mathcal{C}l_{3,1}$.)

The algebra of observables is just the algebra of the Clifford multivectors, that is, multivectors that can be formed from geometric products of the near-frame $\{e_\mu\}$ (by which we mean the local frame within the Witt basis of the full Standard Model). Not all multivectors are observables of course, but all the Dirac bilinear invariants are there, they can be expressed in terms of the Clifford subalgebra generated by the $\{e_\mu\}$.

Notice the Witt basis is basically a set of Grassmann variables, but we will not need the Grassmann calculus since all operations of the spinors we will form from the q, q^\dagger will live in the same algebra, the $\mathbb{C}l_8$, as will our observables. This is a very useful feature of Clifford algebra frameworks, since it means we can dispense with a lot of the technical machinery of category theory functors and mappings (at least until we get to general relativity, although that technical development is not a topic in this philosophical article, we will only have cause to mention the foundational principles of GR later on).

The difficulty with gravity is that we need to port the Gauge Theory Gravity (GTG) over to a theory of the spacetime transformation instructions (the fermions and bosons). There is a functor then from the machinery of GTG, which still directly handles curvature, torsion and geodesics, which are no longer available to us in the Standard Model T4G approach because, recall, in the quantum theory we “throw away” the interior of the spacetime cobordism. Nevertheless, this task is not as daunting as it seems, because GTG is already formulated in terms of the Clifford algebra — the STA or $\mathcal{C}l_{3,1}$ — which is a proper subalgebra of our T4G theory. Thus porting GR to T4G is mainly about handling the couplings correctly,

to get a UV and IR finite theory. In other words, we remain entirely within the same category! The porting over is a morphism within $\mathbb{C}l_8$, and indeed little use is needed for category theory.

There is a wealth of literature showing all of NRQM and RQM can be expressed in this STA (see [15][16] [24–27]). Until recently though, a minimal LR-symmetric Standard Model with chirality and a triality automorphism was elusive. This problem has been solved [2, 8, 12]. (It remains unknown whether the 4D STA alone is sufficient for triality and chirality, we suspect not.)

A first set of 16 primitive idempotents can be formed from the ladder operators defined in Eq.(1), the first ...and after some suitable combinatorial permutations of basis elements, the last are,

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= q_0 Q_0 q_1 Q_1 q_2 Q_2 q_3 Q_3, \\ &\dots \\ v_{16} &= Q_0 q_0 Q_1 q_1 Q_2 q_2 Q_3 q_3. \end{aligned}$$

it is easy to check these are idempotents v_a , $a \in 1, \dots, 16$, and that the Witt basis elements act like number operators on each of these vacua, Here Clifford multiplication is implied, so we are getting mixed grade multivectors from hereon, in general. An even product of two q, q^\dagger will in general result in an element in the even subalgebra of $\mathbb{C}l_8$ (so a grade $k = 0, 2, 4, 6$ or 8 , k -vector, in fact a k -blade).

Each of these “vacua” (primitive idempotents, v_a) define an associated spinor left Ideal Ψ_a , for a fixed $a \in 1, \dots, 16$, via,

$$(\psi_a v_a) x \subseteq \Psi_a v_a, \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{C}l_8.$$

where $\Psi_a = \psi_a v_a$, and the ψ_a are the monomial spinor components (essentially the Dirac spinors) in the even subalgebra that do not annihilate v_a from the left. Each such Ideal Ψ_a contains 8 Dirac–Weyl spinors.

For shorthand we define four characteristic bivector operators,

$$J_i = [q_i, q_i^\dagger], \quad i \in 0, \dots, 3.$$

in terms of which isospin and hypercharge can be defined,

$$\begin{aligned} T_3(\psi) &= \frac{1}{4}(J_3 - J_2) \psi \\ Y(\psi) &= \frac{1}{2}(J_3 + J_2) \psi - \frac{1}{3} \psi (J_1 + J_2 + J_3) \end{aligned}$$

where we see the importance of having $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ generators act on ψ from-the-left, to whit: this does not violate the Coleman–Mandula theorem because $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ generators are constructed from $\{q_2, q_3\} +$ daggers, while the Lorentz algebra is constructed from only $\{q_0, q_1\} +$ daggers, which the definitions (1) make clear.

It is a nice feature of Clifford algebra that we also gain separation of $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ — with generators from $\{q_i, i \in 1, 2, 3\}$ more simply, by action only from the right of ψ . This is obvious to proponents of geometric algebra

who know from the beginnings that rotors transform one-sided (as do spinors) but also act two-sided to perform full rotations on geometric algebra objects. This also explains why *algebraic* spinors are ‘physical’ fermions (it is because spinors are just scaled rotors, see [6]). Here by ‘physical;’ fermion we mean a spacetime transformation instruction, not an actual 4-geon. Quantum mechanics, recall, in T4G theory is a theory of the transformations, not a theory of the ‘physical stuff’ *as noumena*.

(Note that the operators $J_i = [q_i, Q_i]$ are commuting involutions (grade/charge operators) associated with each Witt mode; they are not Jordan generators. (Jordan structure would arise instead from the symmetrized product, $a * b = \frac{1}{2}(ab + ba)$ on observables.)

The spin- z and chiral projectors identify \uparrow, \downarrow , and L/R spinor transforms (in orthodox literature misnamed as “the particles” or “the field quanta”). The quark colors and electric charges are found as usual from the $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ generator eigenvalues and hypercharge operators respectively, the full $\mathfrak{u}(1)$ charge operator is in Blood’s model defined by left-right action on a full Ψ_a ,

$$\mathcal{Q}(\Psi) = \frac{1}{2}J_3\psi - \frac{1}{6}\psi(J_1 + J_2 + J_3). \quad (2)$$

and the Gell-Mann–Nishijima formula follows.

With 8 spinor monomials in each left Ideal, the full \mathcal{Cl}_8 Tableau thus contains two copies of one generation of LR-symmetric Standard Model fermions.

The difference between Blood’s Clifford fibre model and the T4G model is in how the transforms in the far-frame $\{f_\mu\}$ are treated. In the fibre model they are all internal, whereas in T4G they are merely far-away at some other point in spacetime. This interpretative distinction might turn out to be a difference with no difference, but we prefer the T4G view because it includes bare bones quantum mechanics, since we are postulating a 4D spacetime geometric interpretation the $\mathcal{Cl}_{0,1}$ structure as the algebraic shadow of the T4G wormholes, and thus giving rise to the quantum mechanical aspects. This postulate is not optional, because we cannot get triality in \mathcal{Cl}_8 with the correct Standard Model charges otherwise (see [14]), it must be minimally \mathcal{Cl}_8 (that is, minimally, or otherwise beyond the Standard Model). We believe the quantum stochastic dynamics in the Clifford fibre view is not as well motivated, and has to be added as an additional metaphysical postulate.

By contrast, in the T4G theory we provide a spacetime geometric account for the $\mathcal{Cl}_{0,1}$ structure, which is what provides us with a quantum theory with no further postulates needed. It might be regarded as “miraculous” that a demand for a quantum theory can endow the otherwise classical transformations of the Standard Model with the correct charge assignments and triality, but our philosophical journey has always regarded the Standard Model symmetries and quantum mechanics as inseparable, and so while perhaps a miracle of some uniqueness, it was not unexpected, we were searching for this uniqueness. This miracle could disappear of course if experi-

ments reveal more exotic physics beyond the Standard Model.

The QFT gauge field terms for the Lagrangian in the massless UV limit are discussed by Blood [8] and so will not be repeated here. We are not aware of any results different to orthodox Standard Model QFT at this stage, but the \mathcal{Cl}_8 model might yield a novel Higgs mechanism and a way to compute Yukawa couplings.

Before discussing gravity, note that we have been (inadvertently) following almost a Grothendieck track here, the *definitions* given alone almost suffice for a bright student, who could now almost read-off the entire UV limit of the Standard Model.

IV. DO NOT RE-QUANTIZE GRAVITY?

There is not much more to add that is pre-mathematical in this section because the above discussions suggest that the known Standard Model is a quantization of spacetime. This is perhaps only a possible “insight” in a spacetime topology theory like T4G; on the other hand if the theorist imposes spacetime minimalism upon their theory building, then it is less an insight and more a model-tautology. Be that as it may, within the wider pantheon of all possible interpretations of QFT, it would be insightful if we found we did not need to re-quantize gravity. The question being: is this niche in theory-space of non-zero measure? We believe it is, and T4G is in that niche.

We will sketch the resulting theory of ‘already quantized gravity’ here, and leave some of the details of what might happen at the Planck scale to the *even more* speculative remarks in §-VI.A.

The SM is already quantum gravity. Explicitly, the Lorentzian path integral over 4-geometries is exactly the path integral over the Standard Model degrees of freedom. We have no proof of the following yet, but our claim is that the orthodox path integral is a good quantum theory and is UV complete, and that the topology of spacetime is only subject to quantum entanglement (and uncertainty) due to the topology in the Standard Model. The \mathcal{Cl}_8 structure is “good enough” to support this claim, provided no new fundamental symmetries beyond the Standard Model are discovered. This is because considerations of 4-manifold algebraic topology should be able to relate the \mathcal{Cl}_8 algebraic structure to bipartite 4D spacetime topology. At least we see no apparent obstacle.

The euclidean path integral is an analytical tool useful for completely different purposes, namely for the 4D “thermodynamics” of spacetime [28, 29].

Our summary, albeit unformalized and unproven, is that gravity is already quantized, the quantization of gravity is the Standard Model. To re-quantize gravity is redundant and so only invites pathologies. There should still be signatures of gravity-induced entanglement and gravitational superpositions. The superpositions are stochastic effects though, not totally ontolog-

ical. In the T4G theory the superpositions are weakly ontological. This goes beyond Barandes’ strongly epistemic stochastic theory of superpositions.

The EPR effect is impossible in a T4G theory without the entanglement being equivalent to wormhole traversals of *at least* quantum information, that is to say, transformation instructions or weak (as in mild) topology change. The EPR effect involves only weak topology change because the Bell pairings do not change particle types, they only involve an exchange of information about spin orientation and other simpler conserved charges between the pairs.

How so? The reason being that T4G wormholes are probably not completely censored. All interaction in the SM is topology change, this is just a direct result of imposing spacetime minimalism. Thus if there are topological transformations in the empirical phenomenology that are not permitted in 4D spacetime, then they would be no-go theorems against T4G theory. However, such topology change does not obviously admit wormhole traversals. To be consistent with Freidman–Schleich topological censorship [22, 23, 30] and for there to be a possibility of “quantum” traversals of minimal Planck scale wormholes [31] the amount or weight of T4G exotic paths in the path integral would have to be severely limited. This is already the case with interference in the path integral wiping out the weights of the exotic paths. But if there are effectively wormhole traversals of “quantum information” — as is empirically understood in the EPR effect — then effective exotic paths are not physically impossible, and thus do need to be summed over in a proper path integral formulation (see also discussions by Sorkin and others [32–34]).

It is also likely, in our (for now) purely philosophical view, that such exotic paths may also be heavily suppressed, more suppressed than the orthodox Feynman–Hibbs path integral formalism permits. This might one day be testable.

V. COUPLING AND INTERACTIONS

T4G has not previously received a decent interaction model treatment, mainly because we have no clues about the proper spacetime geometrodynamics, because in turn we do not know what the 4-geon topology is precisely. We only to-date have the bare algebra. But the algebra can get us a long way, and is of intrinsic interest because with algebraic couplings (compared with empirical data) we can perhaps gain insights into the underlying spacetime topology, should T4G be some kind of “correct” theory. Alternatively we could gain a no-go theorem, disqualifying T4G theory (suppose say in the event the only consistent couplings turn out to be unphysical).

The closest to a T4G interaction–coupling model we have found is in Jason Blood’s preprint [8], and in Gresnigt’s work on showing topological preon models can be found in the left ideals of Cl_6 and Cl_4 [35]. The preon-

like models provide some highly indirect evidence that there is a T4G topology underpinning the algebraic Standard Model, but that topological theory is not sufficiently well developed yet to be capable of computing coupling constants, but there seems no reason why progress on this could not be made.

Since we have been unable to improve on Blood’s work, we report it here in summary overview, and make some further philosophical remarks that provide a topological 4-geon view of the same — which is a distinct contribution since Blood himself prefers a fibre bundle ontology. Any decent physicist ought to remain agnostic about the ontology, but to make progress we have found it useful to adhere to some imagined ontology. It may be that presently we cannot distinguish our 4D T4G ontology from a fibre bundle theory, in which case the spirit of this paper is to work towards getting some kind of distinction.

At the end of the day, it might just turn out that the T4G worldview is just a different language for expressing a particular fibre bundle ontology. Or vice versa. If so, that would be fine. This stated, to prime readers towards a T4G bias, we offer the suggestion, ahead of reading what is to follow, that there is a distinction immediately that should be experimentally testable, which is that T4G definitely does not claim every single abstract point in spacetime is “endowed” with a gauge fibre. Instead, in T4G theory the fibre bundle theory would be derived as an effective stochastic description of the 4-geon topology.

This is not hard to derive, it is the same as any statistical theory with a spatial, or space-time, probability density function, $\rho(x, t)$. In a statistical model no one is forced to presume the events which are endowed with a measure do in fact occur everywhere with point-wise infinitesimal probabilities. It is perhaps little understood that the QM theories of wavefunctions and spinors *are* statistical theories. Reducing down to the amplitudes does not make QM/QFT less statistical, quite the contrary.

T4G in effect can be treated as *gauge fibre everywhere in spacetime* precisely because the wormhole topology admits weak superposition. To wit: in T4G theory there exist closed timelike curves, only elementary particles cannot traverse them, but elementary particles can certainly traverse nearly closed timelike curves, whereas bulk matter cannot (due to topological censorship [23]). However, weak superposition, or merely the non-Markov stochastic effects of spacetime indivisibility, are sufficient for nature to appear just as if there is 4-geon “fibre” everywhere. If one cannot determine the spacetime topology precisely, then one must assume the 4-geon could be anywhere. This is exactly why gauge fibre theory is applicable (in our view).

How could this be tested? We are not smart enough to yet know! Hence this report to beg for experimental test ideas.

V.A. \mathbb{C} -fibre connexions are (mostly) internal

Blood’s basic idea [8] is that curvature in the Clifford algebra is expressed by means of the orthodox spin connexions, but the curvature is in the internal algebra, not in the ambient spacetime. The exception in the $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$ we favour is in $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ which does involve one Lorentz index. It is not all that much of an exception in the T4G interpretation however, since the “internal” $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$ frame, $\{f_\mu\}$ above, is still regarded as a spacetime Clifford frame, but unobserved as spacetime transform proper, being at the far-end of the wormhole topology. From the point of view of elementary particle phenomenology one must “get through the wormhole” to have sensitivity to the $\{f_\mu\}$ frame, or equivalently the $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ generators in $\{q_2, q_3\}$ and daggers.

Ambient spacetime curvature is presumably “just gravity.” This conceptual view is consistent with T4G theory.

For the gravity sector Blood uses the tetrad and spin connection formulation. We believe this is directly translatable to the Lasenby–Doran gauged-gravity (GG) formulation [36]. We have tried, at least conceptually, to follow the Lasenby–Doran approach, because it can very naturally incorporate spinor theory, in fact the Lagrangian for GG is more naturally obtained beginning with spinors, rather than the metric. In GG one does not require Einstein’s Principle of Equivalence (EPE). Instead one begins with demanding position (PI) and rotation (RI) remapping invariance. Along with the minimal coupling principle (MC) these three principles are sufficient to derive the (EPE). The resulting equations of motion for GG are coordinate independent, and while strange to the unfamiliar eye, the whole approach of GG appears more parsimonious and more elegant than traditional GR.

(This is essentially because the Clifford Geometric Calculus is a very natural, and sometimes simple, way to approach differential geometry, whereby the entire differential structure of a manifold — which need not be smooth — is found in the pseudoscalar of the induced Clifford algebra on the manifold, see for example [37].

The beauty of this approach is that not all that much changes for the spinor sector. The interactions are still “generated” by the curvature, only now in the \mathbb{C} fibres (in the T4G case that is via the wormhole topology, or topological change) and in the stochastic theory the Lagrangian is easy enough to describe as one would using orthodox Standard–Model considerations of renormalization, dimensionality, symmetry, and anomaly cancellation.

By lifting up the spacetime dynamics to a Lagrangian, we are now explicitly choosing to formulate a stochastic theory, this is most clear in the T4G picture, because in T4G gravity the presence of ER=EPR wormholes implies we cannot deterministically time-evolve the particle (or field) variables off a past Cauchy horizon. We need the second future boundary data, and so can only prescribe what that is, and hence then can only compute proba-

bilities. If we compute only amplitudes then according to Barandes’ ISQM scheme we are merely computing indivisible structure aspects, which in the T4G picture is unknowable wormhole topology data.

Unknowable because it cannot possibly be probed due to the topological censorship conjectures [22] (although conjectures⁵, provisional T4G theory would just take them as model axiomatic, for the time being)).

As might be expected though, many parameters remain undetermined, in our T4G case because we do not know the Planck scale topology and hence do not know the geometrodynamics. In the \mathbb{C} fibre case there simply is no ontology available for computing the Yukawa constants. It has to be an empirical QFT theory, at least for now.

V.B. Conformal Couplings

There are exciting developments from two research groups concerning the conformal symmetries in the massless limit. One group (Turok, Boyle et al) at Edinburgh are exploring how imposing CPT symmetry seems to demand conformal invariance via including 36 dimension zero Fradkin–Tseylin scalars to the Standard Model. The other group (Miller & Zubkov) have used these scalar degrees of freedom to couple the fermions to gravity — directly via the vierbein (tetrad), and show how one can compute at least the heaviest quark masses. This is also a mechanism for dynamical symmetry breaking, and so becomes a theory of a non-fundamental composite Higgs mechanism. The Higgs field thus seems to become a property of a dynamic spacetime vacuum.

The requirement that the scalars (having dimension zero, so not Klein–Gordon fields) enter into the Lagrangian with a fourth derivative demands these are not transformations characterizing spacetime topology changing currents, so they are not accounting for propagating particles. (If they were they’d violate Ostrogradsky stability criteria, resulting in the theoretical nightmare of an unstable vacuum which we are guessing no one knows how to simply gauge away.)

The vierbein is a natural object in Clifford algebra, being nothing really but the STA frame field $\{\gamma^\mu\}$ which are precisely the Dirac matrices in the reduced Dirac theory (where only the $\mathbb{C}\ell_{3,1}$ spinor monomials are treated). This field is once again associated with *transformation instructions* in T4G theory. The gravitational action can be accounted for in terms of even more primitive notions, namely: (i) a position covariant gauge, denoted \bar{h} ; and (ii) a rotation covariant gauge, denoted $\bar{\omega}$. These, rather than the metric, are the theory primitives in the

⁵ It is not known to us whether Friedman’s topological censorship can strictly be applied to Planck scale wormholes, but we do not require the censorship to hold at the Planck scale.

Gauge Gravity (GTG) \sim gauge theory of gravity, framework for general relativity, as elegantly expounded upon in the GTG papers of Lasenby, Hestenes, Gull and Doran [36, 38, 39].

In GTG from the position and rotation gauges physical fields can be constructed, which are the Riemann curvatures and the torsion. It is mainly because these more primitive fields are employed that direct coupling to Dirac spinors is possible in this classical GR. In fact in [38] suggest that fermion action coupled minimally to these gauge fields is the more natural way to derive the Einstein equations, and the Einstein Principle of Equivalence (EPE) follows *as a consequence of* these two separate gauges plus the Minimal Coupling Principle.

Another way of putting this, which Hestenes has also emphasized [40], is that diffeomorphism invariance is not a correct physical principle, and this was known to Einstein — in, for example, the Hole Problem [41] — whereas position and rotation remapping invariance is a solid physical principle. Hence one is led to GR via the GTG, rather than via diffeomorphism invariance and the EPE.

Perhaps quite importantly one can also relax the EPE by relaxing the Minimal Coupling Principle? This is how Miller & Zubkov obtain their variety of vacuum condensation, electroweak symmetry breaking and the fermion masses from dynamics. Their method is to account for conformal transformations by directly coupling fermions to the vierbein in the Lorentzian action.

Most physicists might scoff at this for being merely semi-classical quantum gravity, but in T4G context it looks a lot more like the correct theory for quantum gravity, since in T4G we do not place the metric in superposition, since the fermions are already treated stochastically as if they are in superposition, and the fermions (and bosons) are the topology of spacetime.

To further emphasise our distinct point of view, you might appreciate that it is far easier to stick a fictional accounting tool (the ψ) in weird superpositions, rather than an actual physical object! This is T4G in a nutshell. The stochastic degrees of freedom we permit ourselves are what get in superpositions. They are just abstract transformation instructions, propagating “quantum information” so-to-speak. But the underlying reason for this is due to wormhole mediated entanglement between the physical particles, the 4-geons.

What is physical in the theory (according to T4G) are the observable algebra objects, which in T4G + Clifford framework are modelled by just the algebraic gadgets called multivectors (or bilinear covariants) which one can form from composing the Clifford algebra frame basis vectors. In the STA that’s $\{\gamma_\mu\}$ + geometric products. The spinors ψ act upon this algebra of observables, and the physical content is the result of these transformations, hence of M is some multivector, then we can compute (simplifying a little, see [15, Sec.8.2]),

$$\langle M \rangle = \psi M \tilde{\psi}$$

in the Clifford algebra now, not the Hilbert space of ma-

trix algebra. But functorially they’re the same, just different representations.⁶ However, it is very clear in the Clifford algebra QM that it is M that is physical, not the transform instructions ψ . The ψ as-fields are fictions, useful accounting tools.

The main discovery of Turok & Boyle is that including these couplings, in the form of 36 dimension=0 Fradkin–Tseytlin scalars, results in curing the Weyl, trace and vacuum anomalies, but only if there is no fundamental graviton, and no Higgs. Moreover this implies three generations of fermions [1]. This seems like another miracle! But again, from a T4G stance it *was what we expected* and were searching for. Most certainly we alone may have never discovered this “miraculous” vanishing of the UV catastrophes, but historical circumstance of discovery are of no import for the true seeker.⁷ Thus in retrospect there is no miracle at all, it is a form of naturality [43].

What Milel & Zubkov seem to be implying that if we relax the Minimal Coupling Principle, to permit coupling via dimension zero scalars of fermions to the vierbein, then a natural dynamical fermion mass generation mechanism appears at low temperatures, explicitly associated with electroweak symmetry breaking, and thus it is a Higgs mechanism but without the Higgs particle. In the Higgs we thus seem to have a composite field built from these FT scalars and/or massless fermions, or at least the coupling between these.

An unresolved question we have, not in this cited literature, is what exactly the connection is between the FT scalars and the spacetime vacuum?

T4G theory offers a possible resolution worth examining. Assuming T4G theory is valid to some extent, then just as with entanglement, we have very few options for new physics beyond the Standard Model, and so the effect of the FT scalars can really only be local gauging of the expansion and contraction of spacetime, so much like the String Theory dilaton, only now in GTG/GR coupled to the fermions of the Standard Model. Why is this just about the only possible option? The reasons are, (1) as just remarked, there is no other structure in 4D topological geon spacetime than give “give us” new degrees of freedom. There would be if we were permitted more exotic topology other than bipartite wormholes, such as ubiquitous GHZ topology, but this does not seem to be our universe. (2)

These raise lots of research questions we hope bright students take an interest in exploring. For example, why would GHZ (multiparite entangled states) be rare in nature? What are the Tsirelson bounds predicted by T4G theory? Is ER=EPR a robust principle? (see

⁶ The Clifford algebra QM is closer to the Schrödinger picture than Heisenberg rep., at least before translation to the Lagrangian path integral framework.

⁷ He said, “I seek for Layli.” “Alas for thee!” they cried, “Layli is of pure spirit, yet thou seekest her in the dust!” He said, “I seek her everywhere; haply somewhere I shall find her.” [42]

[44–46].) Can we rigorously invert the orthodox view of ER=EPR which we would say was backward: we are saying ER⇒EPR (orthodox holography theorists would say the reverse implication).

Are the constraints T4G places on the exotic paths in Three-Slit interference discernable in the experimental data? Are the empirical tests of superposition compatible with the restricted T4G view than most superposition is just stochastic indivisible dynamics, not actual superposition? What limitations, if any, does T4G theory place on gravitational Aharonov–Bohm type tests, or tests for the actual superposition of the metric, or existence of a graviton that is a fundamental quanta? Can the Yukawa-like couplings be calculated from fundamentals, either with the FT scalars, or otherwise as Jason Blood is pursuing?

These are just some questions one should ask. Our previous paper has a discussion of further possible research directions [6].

V.B.1. Transformations of the fiducial frame

In T4G theory we have already noted the view of the spinors is that they play the role of transforming a fiducial or laboratory Clifford frame $\{\gamma_\mu\}$ onto a physical frame $\{e_\mu\}$. In orthodox QFT this is completely missed, or at best totally mysterious. In T4G Theory it is not so bad, it is a *question*. We know from the structure of QM and QFT that what is transformed are the multivectors in the algebra for the observables. But there is a vital piece of the puzzle missing, because we still do not know the physical topology which our 4D wormhole structure portends to be.

We have seen preon models [35] can be worked into a Clifford algebra representation, which is useful, but not quite what we are seeking in T4G theory. Wormholes are probably not ribbon braids. But it takes no genius to see a close resemblance. Perhaps our 4-geons *are* these ribbons? (How?)

This might however risk confusion. Remember, the T4G spinors are not *the particles*, the spinors are the transformation instructions. Thus what we seek from the spacetime topology is just some kind of wormhole structure that permits topology changing currents that can be then described by the spinor transformations. This is partly a project of mapping algebraic transformations on the multivector algebra of observables to ‘pictures’ of the 4D wormhole topology changes that one would identify as the elementary interactions at *stringy* Feynman vertices. Is any of this possible, or is there some algebraic topology no-go result lurking around the corner?

An interesting new addition to this sort of proto-theorizing is to include local conformal transformations into this topological-preon-wormhole framework. The FT scalars thus might be conceived of as parametrizing local “breathing of spacetime.” This slight anthropomorphisation might not be all that far off, but it would

require significant work to turn into decent mathematical physics. The way Miller & Zubkov use the FT scalars in the SM Lagrangian certainly could be regarded as a conformal gauge symmetry degree of freedom.

At this point in time in development of T4G theory there is not much more we can say. We would like a topology from which the couplings could be *derived* but at present will make-do with some numerology. Even here there is a possum skinning problem. In 4D there seems little doubt we will need 36 Fradkin–Tseytlin scalars, but how should they appear in the Lagrangian? What is the algebraic form of the coupling? Is the form given by Miller & Zubkov the *unique* renormalizable way?

There are some confluences we might use as a guide. First and foremost we would like to centre gravity, since T4GT is essentially as a meme *all gravity and nothing else*.⁸ All gauge forces literally gauge off gravity, as the Witt basis in Eq.(1) suggests, given the T4G doubled STA frame interpretation. In this respect it is notable that the number of degrees of freedom (real parameters) for the Riemann field strength (denoted $R(a \wedge b)$) in the GTG theory is 36 (see [15, Sec.13.5]). This field R is a bivector valued function of a bivector argument $B = a \wedge b$. It is the field strength obtained from the rotation gauge field $\bar{\omega}$. It attains a covariant form by applying the position gauge field \bar{h} to the argument, yielding a covariant $\mathcal{R}(B) = R(\bar{h}(B))$. However, this GTG approach is not directly connected yet to the quantum theory, so the link to the FT scalars is unclear.

The other approach is from the QFT side, where Miller & Zubkov use an indexed FT-scalar ξ_a not contracted but summed (since they’re scalar) over the unitary group index on the spinors. The SM Lagrangian terms being of the form,

$$\bar{\psi}_a(1 + \xi_a)\gamma^\nu D_\nu\psi_a + \text{conjugate} \quad (3)$$

and the vierbein carries the indices, e_ν^μ , that contract with the derivative. With $\xi_a = 0$ we obtain the Minimal Coupled Lagrangian, but then would need explicit Yukawa coupling terms for the masses.

Note with $\xi_a \neq 0$ it is a non-minimal coupling, so in GTG would modify GR with these ‘*quantum*’ corrections. Although as earlier remarked, one can question the use of such language, since really this is just *better GR*. Classical GR was merely the hydrodynamics of the Standard Model [9], the level at which the EPE holds due to Minimal Coupling being operational.

These (3) are terms in the Lagrangian (denoted θ_a) for the quarks and leptons. Miller, Volovik & Zubkov (MVZ) [47] give two other ways of coupling to the FT scalars, one splits LR fermions, as opposed to the above which

⁸ I am indebted to my friend Warren Mosler for this meme. He also provided a superlative analogy: *think of gravity as the stator of a motor and the other forces as the rotor*. A beautiful rhyme there with Clifford algebra.

splits quarks and leptons, and another in which the FT parameters transform under $SU(2)_L$, both of which they reject, in the former case to conserve parity, in the latter because that coupling does not yield the anomaly cancellation. But also note that the quark—lepton split is also the most natural in $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$, for the left-right sides algebraic action we’ve already discussed. This rather begs for a reformulation in pure Clifford algebra (trace operators in Hilbert space \mathcal{H} are scalar projections in $\mathcal{C}\ell$, Dirac adjoints in \mathcal{H} are STA reversions, et cetera).

The way, I believe from reading MVZ[47], the anomaly cancellation counting works is that we have CP symmetry, and the splitting is into quarks + leptons (the FT sectors, let’s say). But then we allow “flavour mixing,” or in this case fermion generation mixing, so each of the ξ_a for a generation type are complex 3×3 matrices, for generation mixing across the three families/generations of quarks and leptons separately. The 3×3 complex matrix (CKM for quarks, PMNS for leptons) rotates between them, with diagonals (intra-generation dominance) and off-diagonals encoding inter-generation transitions (see for example [48]).

In the present MVZ context (ξ_q^{ij} : $i, j \in 1, 2, 3$) parameterize generations in quark sector $u|d, c|s, t|b$ mixing. The diagonal ξ_q^{jj} parameterize mass generation within family j . The off-diagonal ξ_q^{ij} parameterize inter-generation mixing flavor-changing effects post-breaking. Same for ξ_l (leptons). Totalling 36 real scalars from 2 sectors $\times 9$ complex entries $\times 2$ (Re, Im). This mirrors SM Yukawa matrices Y_{ij} , but is in MVZ gravity-sourced via the vierbein.

This makes perfect sense in T4G/ $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ theory in retrospect (we had not thought of FT scalar coupling ourselves) because the T4G/ $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ theory is a pure 4D spacetime theory. Any gravity in it should be coupled to the vierbein, and in T4G theory the fermions *are* gravitational (they are transformation instructions for the spacetime 4-geons). It would be an incomplete theory if not:— a theory of an impotent soldering form.

It is therefore tempting to tie T4G theory to the Turok & Boyle CPT-symmetric Standard Model for cosmology and the same (+ MVZ) Standard Model for particle physics. A naturalness result is on offer if this theory for the FT scalars can be related more closely to the classical GTG approach of Lasenby & Doran, where there are also 36 degrees of freedom in the “vacuum” fields (that is to say, is that just a coincidence?).

The nice kicker here is that the combinatorics come purely from 4D spacetime, thanks to the $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ model. The $\mathbb{C} \cong \mathcal{C}\ell_{0,1}$ structure comes from the bipartite topology of spacetime, which is (in T4G context) exactly what gives us quantum mechanics. But the other numbers also come from 4D spacetime, because in $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ there really is only one consistent way to get maximal numbers of rotations in the spinor ideals, with $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ as the maximal set of rotations acting on-the-right, and $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ the maximal allowed from-the-left, for consistency with Coleman–Mandula theorem requirements, to keep the Lorentz ro-

tations isolated.

We see here the elegance of the Hestenes–T4G Clifford algebra point of view, the allowance of maximality in transformations available in a (Coleman–Mandula) quantum theory, produces all the Goldilocks numbers we’ve been writing about. The naturality is due to taking the spinors to be the transformation instructions, Clifford rotors (under the stochastic hood). T4G adds a stringiness to it all, which implies QM. There is a possible future T4G theorem here: that nature is exploiting all the symmetry available with just Clifford rotors. We would be severely remiss also if not pointing out this was William Kingdon Clifford’s vision — before Einstein and QM came along! It is almost sublime delight then that his algebra is the natural language for his vision.

This is fairly remarkable. Is there a uniqueness theorem here? It certainly smells & tastes like there is!⁹ Provided we impose the constraint that in fundamental physics (without worrying about boundary conditions¹⁰) there is nothing but spacetime. Jason Blood, Anthony Lasenby, and Niels Gresnigt, indeed most Clifford algebraicists working on the Standard Model [26, 49, 50], are of similar mind, that there is a unique Clifford structure that will produce the Standard Model. This is not unimportant or mere bookishness, because although the Clifford algebra is merely a mathematical language, if the SM is unique in this language then by category theoretic functors it is likely unique up to isomorphism in *all* QFT frameworks, which would be a very nice mathematical-*physics* property.

V.B.2. Revisiting the STA

In the spacetime algebra QM we have a reduction to Dirac spinors in the even subalgebra $\mathcal{C}\ell_{3,1}^+$. The primitive idempotents of $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ do not entirely vanish, but instead get re-expressed in a reduced form:

$$\Psi = \psi \frac{1}{2}(1 + \gamma_0)(1 - \sigma_3),$$

γ_0 the *fiducial* STA time basis vector, $\sigma_3 = \gamma_3\gamma_0$ the zt -plane Pauli bivector.

The translation from the conventional STA Dirac spinor to this idempotent basis is non-trivial, there is no simple (rotational) algebraic mapping from one basis to the other, and yet the theories are identical. The difference being that in the idempotent basis the electroweak theory is easier to formulate [51], and it more closely resembles our Witt basis approach to the full Standard

⁹ In private emails, Gresnigt and Blood also seem to be of the same opinion, both working with the 2×4 -fold Witt Clifford basis.

¹⁰ The boundary conditions are not ‘part of’ spacetime *per se*, in our view, which is essentially a Leibniz Principle of Sufficient Reason.

Model. In addition, Lasenby has obtained a workable Strong force theory for these STA spinors, albeit not with chirality nor triality [52].

But we wanted to return to the simpler Dirac theory to connect with the FT scalar anomaly cancellation scheme. What would be required to gain a QFT of this reduced STA quantum field theory? Well, it would be impossible without a unit sedenion to provide the extra *bipartite* structure for three generations, but if that is permitted then the plain vanilla Dirac Theory has much of the Standard Model, possibly not the correct color-charges? In any case, the particle count would appear to be now the same as in $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$, and so FT scalar anomaly cancellation is possible. How then do the FT scalars fit into the simple STA + unit sedenion Dirac Theory?

We have, and will continue to, repeatedly emphasize the Hestenes view: spinors are transformation instructions. Then a dimension=0 FT scalar is naturally a local scale gauge on those instructions:

$$\psi(x) \mapsto e^{\phi(x)/2}\psi(x)$$

which induces

$$\langle M \rangle = \tilde{\psi}M\psi \mapsto e^{\phi(x)}\psi(x)\langle M \rangle$$

for scalar observables (and appropriate weights for others). That seems to be exactly the role of a conformal compensator: it sets local scale. To our knowledge nothing has been worked on in the STA-QM literature in this conformal gauge theory, but it now exists, and does not require unphysical anti-de Sitter spacetime for playing with. Do most physicists just presume Dirac theory is conformal in the massless limit and leave it there? We could ask whether there is a neat trick no one has thought of that can use this simpler FT scalar theory to estimate lepton masses, or play with electroweak symmetry breaking ideas other than the Higgs? All the distinct leptons are right there in the STA, should you choose to accept this Mission.

VI. SPECULATIONS THEN CONCLUSIONS

Classical GR can be taken to be the hydrodynamics of the Standard Model in our view [9, 10], since in our view the entanglement structure *is* the Standard Model structure. In other words, gravity is already a quantum theory. We should not be trying to re-quantize an already quantum theory. We only need to note that GR is the classical description. The UV completion of gravity is thus the UV completion of the Standard Model, but neither side of this completion is fully understood.

In keeping with the ambitions of this present paper as a mere philosophical motivation for younger research groups, we will here only point towards some directions:

1. Mirror boundaries could be the *universal* UV completion?

2. Can the FT scalars be related to the Higgs?
3. Can the Clifford fibre bundle be re-packaged as the statistical dynamics of the T4G spacetime cobordism?
4. Is gravity not in need of quantization?
5. Is T4G gravity “already a quantized theory”?

The last two questions being closely related. Further research directions should be obvious, and Jason Blood [8] is pursuing a few of them, among them the source of the triality automorphism; how the Higgs field arises; how to derive the Yukawa couplings; and an alternative anomaly cancellation scheme. Jason is not using a stringy model, and instead is adopting the more orthodox fibre bundle ontology, but we suspect that is possibly a distinction of little importance. In T4G theory the fibre bundle is merely a statistical description of the indivisible stochastic dynamics of an underlying spacetime wormhole structure (research direction 3), *à la* Jacob Barandes [13].

VI.A. A Bit of Crazy

Although we are arguing T4G is already a quantum stringy theory, hence might inherit aspects of how conventional String theory smooths out interaction regions and thus can yield renormalizable theories even for gravity, there is another possibility which is at least complimentary to this orthodoxy. This is in the CPT-symmetric Universe (CPT-SU) proposal of Turok & Boyle [53]. Turok & Boyle also use Picard-Lefschetz thimbles to tame real-time (Lorentzian) path integrals, thus offering some hope for getting QFT practitioners out of the habit of using the Wick rotation and cut-off crutches, as well as resolving divergences in a very natural way (wave-functions asymptote to zero).

These two ideas suggest something tantalizing though perhaps completely mad. I reckon we can hyper-drive the Tzanavaris Black Hole Mirror [54]. First, note that the black-hole mirror idea is basically the same as the Turok & Boyle CPT-Symmetric big bang: impose CPT symmetry exactly and deduce the consequences.

The thought is what if we just extend the CPT-SU analyticity to Planck energy *in all systems*?¹¹ The QFT path

¹¹ This is motivated by Ted Jacobson doing something similar for the hydrodynamics of entanglement: *any* region of spacetime *anywhere* can be given a fictional horizon structure or causal diamond, from which Einstein’s Equations can be derived with a few reasonable assumptions about vacuum entanglement density.[9] In this derivation we can transport it directly to T4G theory, where Newton’s constant G becomes the inverse of the vacuum wormhole density, or vacuum entanglement density. Turned on its head, this says Newton’s constant as observed is evidence for existence of vacuum wormholes.

integral is, after all, just an effective stochastic treatment of equations of motion, it is not fundamental physics in T4G theory. In the UV limit, just like the CPT-SU, the masses go to zero, and possibly in T4G theory the ER=EPR bridge structure is “unstable” or “completely collapsed” or as Matt Visser seems to hint [31] there is maximal violation of weak energy conditions. I was wondering if — perversely, but wonderfully — this “destroys” quantum mechanics? Then the UV/BigBang/BlackHole are all degenerate in some sense, and reduce to the CPT-Mirror boundary.

One way to break a wormhole is to shove a lot of energy into it — that’s a known result, since a wormhole cannot persist without negative energy — which is just to say a local violation of the weak energy conditions of some sort. Visser [31] has some classical level results on what it takes to collapse a classical GR wormhole, or to keep one stable. But that’s a bit hairy to apply at the Planck scale. Nevertheless, I reckon some very crude first order estimates of decoherence rates (rates of disentanglement or “collapse”) may be possible for T4G by using such known results from classical GR.

For the CPT-Mirrors or UV completion, we do not want the entanglement, we’d prefer GR to “go classical,” since CPT is sufficient to guarantee analyticity, so Einstein’s Equations remain “physical.” No disastrous singularities, just a CPT-bounce. The residual singularity is conformal, so not a problem, it is essentially a mirror boundary.

To temper this madness one can provide probably many counter-arguments. One is that there is a clear tension. If the ultra UV is not quantum mechanical then how would wormhole structure ensure the CPT/mirror boundaries or horizons? After all, the 4-geon is supposed to have wormholes? Right, but we do not know the UV limit of the Standard Model. It could be simpler than $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$. Or it might be something more highly dynamical with wormholes fizzing about all over the show in the massless limit, but then strictly “quantum mechanical” behaviour would again be brought into question. If this seems like we are trying to have our cake and eat it too then you are right, but without 4-geon topology all worked out we are more in a position of defending T4G theory at present rather than actively trying to disprove T4GT.

There is also a pro-conformal exactness dynamical consistency argument. We do need the quantum mechanics (entanglement) for all the physics involved with measurement processes, but this theoretical framework all goes away if there is no “observer” around to make measurements, or equally so many observers that *everything* has become a measurement process. In fact both of these views can be applied in the far UV at a black hole singularity or big bang, since there surely is no stable laboratory one can call a sentient observer, and equally the hot radiation is collapsing wormholes everywhere they form. Although there’s no reason to suppose the wormholes are still not ubiquitous (they are the radiation in

the T4G too, all matter and quanta being 4-geons in our framework).

On an even more philosophical note, this last remark highlights the often confused concept of “a measurement” in orthodox quantum physics texts. There is here, in this extreme example, a clear distinction between a laboratory making a classical measurement, as in quantum computing, and a hot big bang mess where photons pack such high energy *they are* the measurements, by collapsing wormholes, collapsing entanglement. Yet interactions also generate entanglement, so both processes occur at ever faster rate as the matter and radiation go to the full conformal limit. If all this is the case, then we should take the conformal limit seriously, and so there is no proper non-conformal cosmic time $t = 0$ definable, for the radiation and matter the universe never had a beginning, it was always “there” because all that matter was massless and thus experiencing no passing of time. The metaphysical origin of the universe thus cannot be found *within* the universe.

All these speculations are presently mere words. Are we then saying something contradictory that later mathematics will reveal as so? Are we saying we have quantum mechanics but then we do not have quantum mechanics? Our current view is that it is not so stark. Exact conformal symmetry need only occur at very near (in conformal time) to the hypothetical singularity, the mirror boundary in [53], and this is what the Planck scale really is, it is the scale where the local physics becomes exactly conformal. But now everywhere, if we are correct, not just at the big bang. Spacetime is then not “doomed.” Our speculative contention is thus that the Tzanavaris black mirror is universal, so applies not only to the big bang, but to black holes as well, but also in atomic nuclei and even in the vacuum of “empty space.” The mathematical analysis should show that there is a continuous (not necessarily smooth and without phase transitions) approach to exact CPT and conformal invariance. In this case as the previous paragraphs outlined, we do in a poetic sense have both quantum mechanics and not quantum mechanics. We have Goldilocks QM, just the right amount.

Absent hard mathematical results backing these speculations, we can make the story only a little more precise. In T4G theory QM effects are always due to the wormhole topologies (plural, since we do not yet know what the richness in the topology happens to be in our universe, all we know is the Clifford algebraic structure, and then only at low energy and at high energy only modulo consistency requirements). But as just remarked, high energy matter and radiation should collapse these wormholes, destroying entanglement, thus diluting quantum effects. However, wormholes are ubiquitous in T4G, and when one wormhole collapses we can suppose due to CPT symmetry other wormholes will form, it is very hard to argue otherwise. So spacetime never goes to zero wormholes. So it remains quantum mechanical. What changes then in a dynamical spacetime is the conformal structure, it must smoothly, or at least continuously, ap-

proach the CPT mirror. We are now saying *exactly* so! Why? Because the QM effects get scaled away as well, as now every photon is an observer, so-to-speak (but in a precise sense). The Turok–Boyle big bang gets observed into conformal analyticity (again, so-to-speak). In other words, a pathological non-analytic big bang singularity does not exist. The CPT-mirror Turok–Boyle model is perhaps the ultimate topological censorship, physically shielding the entire universe from the most pathological singularity of all.

In addition, our proposal provides a near literal picture for the big bang mirror bounce. This picture relies upon the wormholes not vanishing in the conformal limit, but instead getting ‘hot’ as outlined above. In this case every simple T4G wormhole (let’s say the vacuum wormholes,¹² but this could be the elementary particle 4-geon structure as well) could facilitate the Stueckelberg–Feynman interpretation/mechanism, which is now, in light of our discussion, a micro-statistical basis for the big bang mirror ... and the black hole mirror boundary too. Pair-production is just the ordinary stripped-down version (nature implementing CPT so-to-speak). This does not seem too difficult to accommodate in T4G theory provided wormhole traversals are CPT symmetry respecting.

Evidence in our favour is the Tzanavaris–Turok–Boyle black mirror solution for black holes, which is apparently the only solution for a black hole that respects CPT symmetry [54]. Another picture for the dynamical case (which is not yet well-studied) is that gravitationally completely collapsing matter will, as we just described, become subject to “wild observation” (by ultra-high energy photons if nothing else) which should enforce the Stueckelberg process as also just described. The picture is one of bubbles of void forming in the collapsing region at the ultrahigh densities where our description becomes applicable — where spacetime “observes itself to death,” so-to-speak, creating an expanding sphere of bubbles of mirror bounce for all practical purposes. It seems a perfect marriage of GR and QM. In all cases then, when nature threatens to “blow up” Einstein’s equations, T4G-quantum mechanics and Stueckelberg oblige to keep the evolution tame and analytic. This is our conjecture.

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Before concluding, we would like to emphasize this is a philosophy paper and something of a research project proposal. We’ve asked more questions than we have an-

swered for those who are already familiar with the Clifford algebra QM literature. We have taken a cue from Niel Turok, who has adopted a research strategy of “radical minimalism.” It is a terrifically fun way to do fundamental theory research, but does have a risk of confirmation bias seeking. We ask, “Can a wormhole give us X ?” for any known phenomena X . Thus it is theory building, not testing. Without a full theory to work on at present we are thin on purely mathematical tests.

VI.B. Conclusions

There is nothing in T4G theory that goes beyond known experimental physics, and the theory, though only a proto-theory, appears to be self-consistent. T4G does inherit possible pathologies of GR in the ultraviolet, but this is hardly a no-go in our view because of the mirror boundary proposals of Tzanavaris, Turok & Boyle. T4G also inherits the minimal LR-symmetric Standard Model, and so new particles showing up in successors to CERN and Fermilab could easily refute T4G theory. T4G inherits orthodox quantum mechanics from the Barandes ISQM formulation, and so nothing inconsistent with QM can be derived either. We thus stake the claim that T4G theory is at least as complete and consistent as any other alternative to Quantum Physics writ large.

The Achilles Heel we would like to highlight is the wormhole topology. At present we have no concrete model for the 4-geons, we only have the transformations on their 8-bein frame fields, which we interpret as the quantum fields of orthodox QFT — transformation instructions acting upon the algebra of spacetime observables. It could be that no 4D spacetime concrete geometry exists that is stable with the known low energy masses. But this Paris Arrow awaits some theory which can compute the masses. The same Achilles Heel could be the undoing of T4G should the wormholes be classically traversable or violate empirical bounds like Tsirelson bounds or cluster-decomposition or decoherence rates — all of which remain to be calculated from T4G fundamentals.

One other faint possibility could be multiple slit interference patterns, where Feynman’s sum-over-histories formulation seems to be falsified. Although T4G theory does not fully inherit Feynman–Hibbs SOH completely, there is allowance for exotic trajectories that are summed in the SOH formulation. The call to experimentalists is to push single photon multiple slit interference to ridiculous precision.¹³

¹² Are there really any proper “vacuum wormholes” in T4G theory? Perhaps not.

¹³ Quantum Information Technology (QIT) might also have something to say about T4G theory, but we are not aware of any such

implications beyond superposition coherence times or Tsirelson bounds.

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- [1] L. Boyle and N. Turok, Cancelling the vacuum energy and Weyl anomaly in the standard model with dimension-zero scalar fields, [preprint arXiv:2110.06258 \(2021\)](#).
- [2] B. M. Smith, [The Standard Model spacetime algebra and topology](#), Zenodo doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17971874 (2025).
- [3] L. Boyle, K. Finn, and N. Turok, The Big Bang, CPT, and neutrino dark matter, *Annals of Physics* **438**, 168767 (2022).
- [4] L. Boyle, N. Turok, and V. Vaibhav, Fixed points of classical gravity coupled with a Standard-Model-like theory, [arXiv preprint arXiv:2509.09346 \(2025\)](#).
- [5] K. J. Costello, Quantizing local holomorphic field theories on twistor space, [arXiv preprint arXiv:2111.08879 \(2021\)](#).
- [6] B. M. Smith, Spacetime and Indivisible Stochastic Quantum Mechanics (2025).
- [7] B. M. Smith, [Spacetime EPRB Correlations](#), Zenodo preprint doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17971842 (2025).
- [8] J. Blood, A minimal complex-fiber geometric algebra model of the standard model and dark matter [10.5281/zenodo.17871768](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17871768) (2025).
- [9] T. Jacobson, Entanglement equilibrium and the Einstein equation, *Physical review letters* **116**, 201101 (2016).
- [10] T. Jacobson and M. Visser, Spacetime equilibrium at negative temperature and the attraction of gravity, *International Journal of Modern Physics D* **28**, 1944016 (2019).
- [11] P. Janotta and H. Hinrichsen, Generalized probability theories: what determines the structure of quantum theory?, *Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and Theoretical* **47**, 323001 (2014).
- [12] N. Gresnigt and L. Gourlay, Modelling three fermion generations with S_3 family symmetry within $Cl(8)$, in *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Vol. 2912 (IOP Publishing, 2024) p. 012019.
- [13] J. A. Barandes, The stochastic-quantum correspondence, [preprint arXiv:2302.10778 \(2023\)](#).
- [14] L. Gourlay and N. Gresnigt, Algebraic realisation of three fermion generations with S_3 family and unbroken gauge symmetry from $Cl(8)$, *The European Physical Journal C* **84**, 1129 (2024).
- [15] A. Lasenby and C. Doran, *Geometric Algebra for Physicists* (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 2003).
- [16] D. Hestenes, Real Dirac theory, *Advances in Applied Clifford Algebras* **7**, 97 (1997).
- [17] D. Hestenes, Spin and uncertainty in the interpretation of quantum mechanics, *American Journal of Physics* **47**, 399 (1979).
- [18] D. Hestenes, Gyromagnetics of the electron clock, *IEEE Access* (2025).
- [19] G. Aubrun, L. Lami, C. Palazuelos, and M. Plávala, Entanglement and superposition are equivalent concepts in any physical theory, *Physical Review Letters* **128**, 160402 (2022).
- [20] M. J. Hadley, The logic of quantum mechanics derived from classical general relativity, *Found. Phys. Lett.* **10**, 43 (1997).
- [21] M. J. Hadley, Topology change and context dependence, *International journal of theoretical physics* **38**, 1481 (1999).
- [22] J. L. Friedman, K. Schleich, and D. M. Witt, Topological censorship, *Physical Review Letters* **71**, 1486 (1993).
- [23] J. Friedman and A. Higuchi, Topological censorship and chronology protection, *Annalen der Physik* **518**, 109 (2006).
- [24] C. Doran, A. Lasenby, and S. Gull, States and operators in the spacetime algebra, *Foundations of physics* **23**, 1239 (1993).
- [25] C. Doran, A. Lasenby, S. Gull, A. Challinor, and S. Somaroo, Spacetime algebra and electron physics, in *Advances in Imaging and Electron Physics*, Vol. 95, edited by P. W. Hawkes (Academic Press, 1996) pp. 271–386.
- [26] J. R. Chisholm and R. S. Farwell, A spin gauge model of a family of particles, *Advances in applied Clifford algebras* **18**, 543 (2008).
- [27] A. Challinor, A. Lasenby, S. Gull, and C. Doran, A relativistic, causal account of a spin measurement, *Physics Letters A* **218**, 128 (1996).
- [28] L. Boyle and N. Turok, Thermodynamic solution of the homogeneity, isotropy and flatness puzzles (and a clue to the cosmological constant), *Physics Letters B* **849**, 138442 (2024).
- [29] N. Turok and L. Boyle, Gravitational entropy and the flatness, homogeneity and isotropy puzzles, [preprint arXiv:2201.07279 \(2022\)](#).
- [30] E. Woolgar, Topological censorship and higher genus black holes, *Physical Review D* **60**, 104039 (1999).
- [31] M. Visser, S. Kar, and N. Dadhich, Traversable wormholes with arbitrarily small energy condition violations, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **90**, 201102 (2003).
- [32] R. D. Sorkin, Quantum mechanics as quantum measure theory, **9**, 3119 (1994).
- [33] U. Sinha, C. Couteau, T. Jennewein, R. Laflamme, and G. Weihs, Ruling out multi-order interference in quantum mechanics, *Science* **329**, 418 (2010).
- [34] R. Sawant, J. Samuel, A. Sinha, S. Sinha, and U. Sinha, Nonclassical Paths in Quantum Interference Experiments, **113**, 120406 (2014).
- [35] N. G. Gresnigt, Topological preons from algebraic spinors, *The European Physical Journal C* **81**, 506 (2021).
- [36] A. Lasenby, C. Doran, and S. Gull, Gravity, gauge theories and geometric algebra, *Phil.Trans.Roy.Soc.Lon. A* **356**, 487 (1998).
- [37] D. Hestenes, The shape of differential geometry in geometric calculus, in *Guide to Geometric Algebra in Practice* (Springer, 2011) pp. 393–410.
- [38] A. Lasenby, C. Doran, and S. Gull, Gravity, Gauge Theories and Geometric Algebra, [arXiv preprint gr-qc/0405033 \(2004\)](#).
- [39] D. Hestenes, Gauge gravity and electroweak theory, in *The Eleventh Marcel Grossmann Meeting: On Recent Developments in Theoretical and Experimental General Relativity, Gravitation and Relativistic Field Theories* (World Scientific, 2008) pp. 629–647.
- [40] D. Hestenes, Gauge theory gravity with geometric calculus, *Foundations of Physics* **35**, 903 (2005).
- [41] H. Gomes, The hole argument meets Noether’s theorem, [arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.10970 \(2024\)](#).

- [42] Bahá'u'lláh, *The Seven Valleys and the Four Valleys* (Bahá'í Publishing Trust, Wilmette, IL, 1945) translated in consultation with 'Alí-Kuli Khán; authorized edition.
- [43] A. Borrelli and E. Castellani, The practice of naturalness: A historical-philosophical perspective, *Foundations of Physics* **49**, 860 (2019).
- [44] L. Susskind, Copenhagen vs Everett, teleportation, and ER=EPR, *Fortschritte der Physik* **64**, 551 (2016).
- [45] J. Sonner, Holographic Schwinger effect and the geometry of entanglement, *Physical Review Letters* **111**, 211603 (2013).
- [46] D. Jafferis, A. Zlokapa, J. D. Lykken, D. K. Kolchmeyer, S. I. Davis, N. Lauk, H. Neven, and M. Spiropulu, Traversable wormhole dynamics on a quantum processor, *Nature* **612**, 51 (2022).
- [47] J. Miller, G. E. Volovik, and M. A. Zubkov, Fundamental scalar field with zero dimension from anomaly cancellations, *Phys. Rev. D* **106**, 015021 (2022).
- [48] G. Castelo-Branco and D. Emmanuel-Costa, Flavour Physics and CP Violation in the Standard Model and Beyond, in *Lectures on Particle Physics, Astrophysics and Cosmology: Proceedings of the Third IDPASC School, Santiago de Compostela, Spain, January 21–February 2, 2013* (Springer, 2014) pp. 145–186.
- [49] O. C. Stoica, The standard model algebra–leptons, quarks, and gauge from the complex Clifford algebra $Cl(6)$, *Adv. Appl. Clifford Algebras* **28** (2018).
- [50] C. Furey, Standard model physics from an algebra?, preprint [arXiv:1611.09182](https://arxiv.org/abs/1611.09182) (2016).
- [51] D. Hestenes, Space-time structure of weak and electromagnetic interactions, *Foundations of Physics* **12**, 153 (1982).
- [52] A. Lasenby, Some recent results for SU(3) and octonions within the geometric algebra approach to the fundamental forces of nature, *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences* (2022).
- [53] L. Boyle, K. Finn, and N. Turok, CPT-symmetric universe, *Physical review letters* **121**, 251301 (2018).
- [54] K. Tzanavaris, L. Boyle, and N. Turok, Black Mirrors: CPT-Symmetric Alternatives to Black Holes, [arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.09558](https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.09558) (2024).